

Original Article

NEED TO EQUIP OFFICE TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT STUDENTS IN NIGERIA WITH DIGITAL SKILLS FOR MAXIMUM PRODUCTIVITY IN THE GLOBAL WORKPLACE

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Abstract

This study on the need to equip Office Technology and Management (OTM) students in Nigeria with digital skills for maximum productivity in the global workplace was necessitated by the skills gap between industry and graduates of the programme in the digital era as a result of which many of them remain unemployed for a long time. The globalized office and business environments have become extensively digitalized making it difficult for OTM students, as future office managers, who lack adequate digital skills to secure employment and progress smoothly in the current era. The study reviewed the concepts of Office Technology and Management (OTM) and digital skills to highlight their relatedness. Office Technology and Management refers to programme of study in Nigerian tertiary educational institutions designed to equip students with relevant skills for employment in various fields of endeavor especially as office managers. On the other hand, digital skills refer to the ability to effectively use digital devices, communication applications and the internet to access, manage, create and share information. The study found that duties of office managers (OTM graduates) have transformed beyond the previously popular routines due to the advent of Information and Communication Technology which has made digital skills acquisition a major requirement for success in employment. Consequently, it was concluded that without adequately equipping OTM students with digital skills, most of the graduates will not fit into and effectively perform their current roles. Finally, the study recommended among others that management of Tertiary Educational Institutions should adequately provide ICT infrastructure and tools for lecturers and instructors that are proficient in digital skills as well enabling environment for OTM programme to facilitate hands-on practical experiences by students for adequate acquisition of digital skills.

Keywords: Office Technology and Management Students , Digital employability skills, Maximum productivity and Global workplace

Introduction

The problem of unemployment in Nigerian has

reached a dimension where the expectations of gainful employment in positions directly related to the disciplines of study among fresh graduates are dimmed. Ubulom and West (2021) observed that the world of work is more complex and that newer approaches to work and learning are in high demand

than before, making most educational institutions to imbue their students with functional lifelong learning Skills they need to survive and meet the changes. The present office environment is witnessing drastic changes to the old methods of performing tasks as a result of the infusion of information and communication technology (ICT) tools paving way to new methods. These new methods require new skills, competences and knowledge to perform and succeed in the modern office, hence the call for training and preparation of prospective office workers to acquire relevant skills, knowledge, and experiences needed to perform in the automated office (Ubulom & West, 2021). This clearly shows that the requisite skills for jobs of yester years are apparently different from the skills needed for today's office. Job opportunities of yester years are virtually non-existent on one hand, and a great number of graduates may not have acquired the requisite employability skills needed by the employers of labour on the other hand (Osere, 2017). Employability which requires possession of requisite skills and abilities to secure and progress in employment is currently being influenced by the evolution of ICT and in the current office and business environments. The advent of ICT has increased the demand for technologically skilled employees in the world of work. Consequently, to be employable as an office manager, graduates of Office Technology and Management (OTM) need to possess the requisite digital employability skills in order to be able to fit into the modern technological era. Office Technology and Management (OTM), as a new nomenclature for Secretarial Studies came into existence in 2004, making the secretarial profession vast and highly demanding than it was in the past because of the dynamic nature of the world. Therefore, the use of archaic and slow manual office machines and equipment has given way to highly sophisticated ICT resources. Ejeka (2021) averred

that what led to the need for the change in the nomenclature and course contents of the programme from Secretarial Administration to OTM was the persistent yearnings from stakeholders (employers of labour and professional bodies). Many unemployed youths seem not to possess the necessary skills which the modern economy demands. Eze and Ononye (2021) agreed that one of the main causes of unemployment among Office Technology and Management (OTM) graduates is lack of employability skills. Secretarial studies was changed to OTM so as to bridge that gap by providing a functional training that would help the graduates of OTM make a career in office management. The world of work today as ruled by ICT is a complex one and as such requires individuals to obtain the kind of education that will equip one with knowledge and skills in order to be functional in the society. Office Technology and Management formerly referred to as Secretarial Studies in Nigeria evolved out of a need to meet the technological and managerial demands of today's workplace. With digital revolution altering conventional workplace functions and designing new jobs, there is a pressing need for secretaries to develop and deepen their technical skills to advance work quality, drive creativity and stay employable. A secretary with a growth mindset will be able to plug the skills gap and creates more exciting employment opportunities for himself or herself in the future office. The knowledge and skills learnt by OTM graduates in formal schools are not adequate to meet every demand of their daily activities. As a result of this, there is need for continuous improvement as human learning is continuous and lifelong. More so, the tremendous rates at which scientific and technological changes are taking place make it essential for office managers to constantly learn, unlearn and re-learn new skills through training in order to function well in this e-driven world.

The Concepts of Office Technology and Management (OTM) and Office Managers

OTM programme in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions was designed to impart the youths with practical and employability skills. OTM is an integral component of business education programme that is offered in colleges of education, polytechnics, and universities primarily to educate and train students to become competent office managers as well as business educators (Okoli, 2019). OTM is an efficient, effective, productive and functional education which leads itself to self-employment, self-reliance, paid employment and consequently self-actualization (Oyedele & Fadare, 2018). Thus, the OTM programme can be viewed as a training or education programme that ensures that an individual is impacted with the right skills and attitudes needed for transition from school to work and for advancement in the OTM career path. The goal of OTM is primarily to produce competent, skillful and dynamic office managers, office administrators and businessmen and women that will effectively compete in the world of work. OTM programme was designed to prepare the graduates (office managers) for office work in public and private sectors of the economy. In view of the above, OTM programme is an educational programme meant for the acquisition of knowledge, skills, office ethics and competencies needed to prepare the individual to enter gainful employment in specific business and office occupation and contribute meaningfully to national development. This implies that students must possess office skills that will enable them to perform successfully as a secretary or office manager in a modern office. Therefore, office technology and management as a programme prepares students to possess employable skills which are germane to their successful performance in a modern office or world of work right from the school that makes them suitable office managers. An office manager or a

secretary is a member of staff who is concerned with the preparation, preservation and transmission of different types of office documents as well as conventional secretarial duties of confidential nature at various levels in an organization. This implies that a qualified secretary should possess basic office technology skills, have sufficient knowledge of the operations of all departments within the organization where he/she works (Ejeka, 2017). Office managers are individuals that are professionally trained in the management of information. Secretaries are found in virtually all business organizations and are responsible for the information management system which in recent time is being automated and requires the use of various Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilities. The rapid growth and affordability of ICTs have also resulted to a change in the role of a secretary in today's workplace. For office managers to be able to perform their duties and make meaningful contributions to the success of the organizational goals, they also need to acquire the relevant digital employability skills.

Concept of Digital Employability Skills

Skill is manual dexterity through repetitive performance of an operation. It is an organized sequence of actions and proficiency executed and usually displaying a flexible but systematic temporal patterning (Ugwuanyi in Ezeh et.al 2021). To possess a skill is to demonstrate the habit of acting, thinking and behaving in a specific activity in such a way that the process becomes natural to the individual through repetition or practice. The relevance of skill acquisition in OTM cannot be overemphasized. Skills and office competencies acquired in the programme prepare its recipients with multi-skills necessary to function efficiently in the world of work. Analysts have argued that in Nigeria generally, the skills that job seekers possess do not match the needs and demands of employers. This means that the need for digital skills should be

encouraged in Nigerian students especially in OTM students to increase the chances of employment.

Digital skills include the knowledge and ability to decide information needs from digital technology sources, and to properly use digital tools and facilities to input, access, organize, integrate and assess digital resources as well as to construct new knowledge as stated by Ocholi, Aina and Ezeani (2022). Mcquaidin Ubulom and West (2021) defined digital skills as the transferable skills needed by individuals to make them 'employable'. Iberdrola in Ocholi, Aina and Ezeani (2022) claimed that digital skills are not just about learning and developing technological skills but they also involve the acquisition of knowledge, values, attitudes, regulations and ethics about ICT so as to get the best out of technology. Vasanthakumari (2019) opined that the digital skills required for effective performance of an office manager in the world of work are soft and hard skills. Hard skills are the technical skills individuals use each day to perform their job. Some examples would be computer skills or procedural knowledge applied in job. Unlike hard skills, which can be proven and measured, soft skills are intangible and difficult to quantify and they help facilitate human connections. In most competitive job markets, recruitment criteria do not stop at technical ability and specialist knowledge. Recruiters will be looking for people who can become leaders, and leadership, itself, depends on several key soft skills (Vasanthakumari, 2019). Chigbuson, Timya and Silas (2018) revealed that employers of labour are of high demand of graduates that are work ready and who have both intellectual capacity and are also equipped with ICT skills.

Today, with the help of ICT, organizations have moved forward using digital technologies such as the internet, artificial intelligence and big data. Many jobs will automatically be with digital technologies (Ezeh, Ezeahurukwe & Ameh (2021). The authors

assert that less than 5 percent of jobs will be fully automated; however, about 60 percent of work will be semi-automated. The authors further stated that over the next few years, the employment landscape will change, with the world of work emphasizing the importance of digital employability skills as regards the employment of office managers.

Digital Employability Skills Needed by the Future Office Managers for Maximum Productivity

Employability skills are personal qualities that make people employable. They are sometimes referred to as soft skills, transferable or non-technical skills because they are different from technical knowledge and skills and can be applied to almost any job in any industry (Ezeh, Ezeahurukwe & Ameh, 2021). Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2019) asserted that occupation specific skills are no longer sufficient for graduates of OTM to meet the needs of digital world of work, and that, it takes a set of employability skills. Employability skills and qualifications will be able to contribute positively in the digital age workplace. Many jobs in the digital business will be required to have more complex skills known as employability skills. Demands of the new contexts and trends such as current day industry require OTM graduates who can fulfill the demands of the new contexts and trends, such as digital business. Higher vocational education institutions are increasingly expected to engage with the challenges of the digital business world. Employability skills are not just to get a job, but also how to succeed and survive in a career in the work place. Higher vocational educational institutions are often criticized for not preparing graduates of OTM who are supposedly future office managers with various skills according to the contexts and trends in the current world of work. The facts show that there is employability skill gap between those possessed by the graduates and

those needed by the world of work (Jewell, Reading, Clarke & Kippist, 2020).

In the light of the above, Ubulom and West (2021) outlined the following skills and office competencies need of OTM to include, ability to use ICT equipment for communication, ability to manage information at the right time, ability to recognize and utilize office automation, ability to communicate effectively, using oral and written skills, ability to acquire management and supervisory skills, knowledge of accounts, costing and preparing financial statement, ability to acquire the knowledge of law and ability to recognize trends such as technological trends and government action amongst others. In achieving these skills, it is expected that certain modern office machines/facilities are to be used in teaching and learning in the OTM programme.

Digital employability skills needed by future office managers as highlighted by Ezeh, et al (2021) include:

1. **Electronic Record Management Skills:** An electronic record is a record that can be manipulated, transmitted or processed by a computer. It is written on magnetic or optical medium (including magnetic tapes, cassettes, CD Roms, hard disks e.t.c) recorded in binary code, accessed using computer software and hardware. This can be easily manipulated either updated; deleted, e.t.c. Electronic records management often referred to as ERM or Records Information Management (RIM) is an essential part of organizational business compliance effort. Wamukoya and Mutula in Ezeh et al (2021) observed that lack of knowledge about electronic records keeping and management is a major obstacle in the employment of office managers today and in the future. Records should always be available, protected and managed effectively so as to ensure effective performance of job in modern office.

2. **Photo Based Social Media Skills**

For OTM graduates to remain relevant in today's office, there is need for the acquisition of skills on the application of photo based social media resources. Photo based social media resources is a great resource that can enhance secretaries duties in the modern office for optimum productivity. Social media and technology are integral parts of daily office routine and integrating the use into the classroom and office is more natural than before.

The photo based social media resources for the performance of secretarial duties for today's OTM graduate secretaries include: Facebook which is an American online social media and social networking service based in Menlo Park, California. WhatsApp messenger, or simply WhatsApp is an American freeware, cross platform messaging and voice over service owned by Facebook, Inc. For secretaries to continue to be relevant, there is need to possess ability in this regard.

3. **Video based Social Media Resources**

Video is a device where the moving image has been keeping people entertained over a century. Today, however a look at any social media platform will display video clips that give clues about businesses. Video based social media resources has influenced the ways in which messages are communicated on the social media. Infact, video has become one of the most teaching and learning and advertising channels on the social media. Video content is now integral to teaching and learning organizational behavior. Graduates of OTM can greatly benefit from the use of video based social devices for ease of work in the office as these help secretaries to have access to replay or watch videos related to secretarial practice and principles. Office managers can learn new office procedures which will continue to make them relevant in the world of work at any particular point in time using YouTube. Recording and videoing, teaching/learning sessions and the production of video tutorials can tremendously increase effective

learning process as secretaries have the option to download and play video tutorials over and over again until the content stick to their head.

4. Software Management Skills

Software is a collection of data or computer instructions that tell the computer how to work. This is in contrast to physical hardware from which the system is built. In computer and software engineering, computer software is all information processed by the computer systems, programmes and data computer softwares include programmes, libraries and related non-executable data, such as online documentation or digital media. Computer hardware and software require each other and cannot yield the required result if separated, thereby the need for the modern secretary to possess knowledge on how to manipulate the two is essential.

Developing Digital Skills among Office Managers in the 21st Century

There are a huge variety of skills that can be considered as digital skills. UK Study Centre (2021) stated the digital skills to include: skills to send emails securely, use email attachments, and post on social media; handle information and content, use search engines, understand that not all online content is reliable, access content across devices and on the cloud; set up accounts online, fill in online forms; find solutions to problems using tutorials/chat and improve productivity; and keep passwords secure, take precautions against viruses among others.

According to New Jersey Institute of Technology in Ocholi, et al (2022), one of the several ways to close skills gap among office managers is by re-skilling or up skilling to compete in the marketplace. For those already engaged, the onus remains on companies to up skill them for relevance, while some ambitious employees may take the initiatives of self- sponsorship training to improve themselves. Office managers need to invest in themselves, because when they do, they take that with them for the rest of

their lives. The following are some of the various ways by which the 21st century secretaries can adopt to develop their digital skills as observed by different scholars:

1. Take free Online Courses: TechBoomers (2018) claimed that some websites have interactive tools such as The Skills Toolkit, FutureLearn, Google Digital Garage, and BT Skills for Tomorrow, TechBoomers, to help one learn.
2. Certificate Programs: Gross in UK Study Centre (2021) noted that the key to preparing students for the digital industry is early exposure inside and outside the classroom.
3. Make an Effort to Use Technology for your Job: UK Study Centre (2021) viewed that a person can make it a point of browsing the World Wide Web daily in order to improve efficiency, integrate digital technologies into his or her job or personal endeavours. Digital skills needs of the 21st century secretaries under the following subheads: Emailing Skill, Social Media Management Skill, Blogging Skill, Digital Marketing and Social Marketing Skill, Mobile Skill, Business Data Analytical Skill, Coding Skill, Cloud Skill, Artificial Intelligence Skill, Content Management System (CMS) like Word Press Skill, Showcasing a Portfolio of Work Skill, Search Engine Marketing Skill and Content Marketing Skill (Ezeh et al, 2021). FutureLearn (2020) stated that digital skill boosts the career of those who want to embrace the flexibility of freelance work, enhances personal and professional skills that gives more options for getting a job.

Conclusion

Graduate employability has become one of the central issues for so many years now. Training institutions offering OTM need to make adequate efforts to meet the identified challenges one of which is developing students' employability skills to help the graduates function effectively as office managers. Functions of office managers have

become broader in recent times, as a result of the infusion of ICT resources in modern offices; therefore their need for digital skills for effective performance cannot be overemphasized. Acquisition of these digital competences is of paramount importance since it will make them have job satisfaction, achieve maximum result which will in turn lead to optimum productivity. Office managers need digital skills in order to be proficient in their duties and remain relevant in the global workplace. They should acquaint themselves with new digital skills in the areas of manipulative technology and communication competencies in order to market image of their organizations to the global community. Despite the fact that technology utilization has revolutionized the traditional roles of secretaries, professional secretaries with digital skills still remain highly indispensable in any establishment since their roles are the pivot of office activities. The efficiency and effectiveness of the office manager in every business organization depends largely on the availability of office technologies as well as their possessed digital skills and competencies to handle these office technologies. The current automated offices require that for secretaries to remain and functional, they must be competent in manipulative technology, communication and professional skills. This study

REFERENCES

Amiaya, A.O. (2016). Availability and utilization of new technology in business education for teaching office technology and management in Delta State Polytechnics. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 3(2), 64 – 72.

Chigbuson, A. J., Timya, N., & Silas, T. N. (2018). Information and communication technology skills needed by office technology and management students for self-sustenance and

therefore concludes that training institutions can adequately equip OTM students with employability digital skills; they will be in a position to drive maximum productivity in different organizations globally as future managers.

Recommendations

Based on the detailed examination of this topic and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Tertiary institutions should adequately provide ICT resources and an enabling environment for OTM programme to churn out graduates with the required employability skills to reduce graduate unemployment in Nigeria.
2. OTM graduates should endeavour to acquire modern office skills necessary for them to function effectively in the global workplace.
3. OTM lecturers should adequately expose students to relevant hard and soft skills for effective performances in a modern office upon graduation.
4. Government should encourage retraining of OTM lecturers to acquire requisite digital skills since they cannot give what they do not have.
5. Government should provide enough funds to equip tertiary institutions with relevant ICT resources and internet connection to facility acquisition of digital skills among students.

national development. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 5(2), 206 – 213.

Ejeka, C. A. (2017). Office management competencies required of office technology and management graduates in Imo State civil service. Unpublished M.Ed dissertation presented to the Department of Business Education, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki.

Ejeka, C. A. (2021). Office management skills required of office technology and management

- graduates in Ebonyi State civil service. Nigerian journal of Business Education, (NIGJBED), 8(1), 183 – 189.
- Eze, T. I. & Ononye, A. O. (2021). Employability skills required of office technology and management graduates by managers of small scale enterprises in Anambra State. NAU Journal of Technology & Vocational Education, 6(1), 60 – 68.
- Ezeh, P. C., Ezeahurukwe, N. L. & Ameh, A. O. (2021). Digital employability skills required by future secretaries for optimum productivity in business organization. Nigerian journal of Business Education, (NIGJBED), 8(2), 187 – 198.
- FutureLearn (2020). The complete guide to digital skills. Retrieved online from <https://www.futurelearn.com/info/blog/the-complete-guide-to-digital-skills>.
- Ocholi, J. M., Aina, M. A. & Ezeani, N. S. (2022). Secretarial profession and the training needs of secretaries for the future office work. Nigerian journal of Business Education, (NIGJBED), 9(2), 159 – 165.
- Okoli, C.E. (2019). Office technology and management curriculum contents and the use of modern information communication and technology facilities among students of Polytechnics in Nassarawa State, Nigeria. Association of Business Educators of Nigeria, Conference Proceedings 6(1), 624 – 631.
- Osere, C. N. (2017). Entrepreneurship education curriculum for Employability: Teachers as catalysts. Nigerian Journal of Business Education, 4(2), 77 – 84.
- Oyedele, J. F. & Fadare, G. O. (2018). New technologies in teaching and learning of office technology and management. Nigerian Journal of Business Education, 5(1), 264 – 273.
- TechBoomers (2018). 17 great ways you can work to enhance your digital skills. Retrieved online from <https://techboomers.com/ways-to-enhance-your-digital-skills>.
- Theron, G. (2016). 5 factors that will define the office of the future. Retrieved online from <https://www.felix.net/project-news/5-factors-defining-the-office-of-the-future>.
- Ubulom, W. J. & West, J. J. (2021). Modern office skills and employability of secretaries amongst graduating office technology and management students in Rivers State. International Journal of Innovative Information Systems & Technology Research, 9(4), 61 – 69.
- Vasanthakumari, S. (2019). Soft skills and its application in work place. World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 3(2), 66 – 72.